

An analysis of voltage source inverter switches fault classification using short time Fourier transform

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ABSTRACT

The dependability of power electronics systems, such as three-phase inverters, is critical in a variety of applications. Different types of failures that occur in an inverter circuit might affect system operation and raise the entire cost of the manufacturing process. As a result, detecting and identifying inverter problems for such devices is critical in industry. This study presents the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) for fault classification and identification in three-phase type, voltage source inverter (VSI) switches. Time-frequency representation (TFR) represents the signal analysis of STFT, which includes total harmonic distortion, instantaneous RMS current, RMS fundamental current, total non harmonic distortion, total waveform distortion and average current. The features of the faults are used with a rule-based classifier based on the signal parameters to categories and detect the switch faults. The suggested method's performance is evaluated using 60 signals containing short and open circuit faults with varying characteristics for each switch in VSI. The classification results demonstrate the proposed technique is good to be implemented for VSI switches faults classification, with an accuracy classification rate of 98.3%.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Voltage source inverter (VSI) is commonly used to convert a DC voltage into an AC voltage with varying magnitude and frequency [1]–[6]. As a single failure in the converter components will result in a fault in the overall system, the system reliability of these converters is critical [7]–[15]. As a result, in several crucial procedures, the VSI must be able to operate continuously even under malfunctioning situations [16]–[19]. Semiconductor switches and aluminium capacitors are the two most critical components of a voltage source inverter. Soldering joint and semiconductor failures account for more than 34% of all malfunctions and failures [20]–[24].

The voltage supply inverter, like any other power electronics energy conversion device, is directly exposed to excessive stress elements such as physical stress and thermal, electrical [25]–[29]. Power semiconductor switches, particularly and insulated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs), and meta-oxide semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) are the most sensitive components in the VSI, resulting in greater failure rates [30]–[35]. Power switch faults are divided into two types: short circuit faults (SCFs), and open circuit faults (OCFs) [36]–[41]. Moreover, OCF arises as a result of driver failure, which retracts the bonding wires during thermic cycling by a SCF caused by rupture or age [42]–[45]. OCF poses risk to the key components of a energy transfer, and healthy converter to load is often achieved even in a deteriorated state [46]–[48]. However, if such failures persist for an extended period of time, more damage to the converter may occur, resulting in an utter stop in the worst-case scenario [49]–[53]. As a result, identifying and detecting such failures is suggested to avoid severe damage in power converters [54]–[58].

Numerous studies have proposed various methods for three-phase inverter open circuit (OC) failure diagnostics, including model-based algorithms and signal processing-based algorithms especially time-frequency domain analysis [31], [59]–[65]. Several researchers have presented model-based methods for diagnosing faulty switches through all the study of the system model, which demonstrate excellent accuracy and strong applicability but require a precise mathematical model or additional hardware [12], [66]–[72]. Previous model-based techniques, on the other hand, are susceptible to system characteristics and have limited detection accuracy [73]–[75]. Prior knowledge regarding converter specifications (parasitic resistances, inductances, capacitances) is critical for the improvement of model-based algorithms, but difficult to gain from the existing system [16], [44], [76]. Shahbazi *et al.* [49] proposed a model-based approach for detection of fault using a field-programmable gate array (FPGA) based on time and voltage criteria. Nevertheless, when compared to an application specific integrated circuit (ASIC) platform with the same design specifications, the FPGA does not provide fast execution, reduced power consumption, or lower mass manufacturing costs [1], [77]–[84]. Additionally, Jiang *et. al* and Lei *et. al* stated in [85], [86] that the typical convolution neural network (CNN) analysis for OC had a flaw with the model-based algorithm since the required the size of the sample data used for model training was considerable and prone to overfitting.

There is no requirement to find prior information of converter parameters in this proposed method, thus a development of signal processing fault diagnostic method is presented. The proposed method, known as the short-time fourier transform (STFT), is based on time-frequency domain analysis [87], [88]. The suggested method will discover OC faults in converter topologies by classifying specified signal parameters. Furthermore, combining STFT analysis with a ruled-based classifier may overcome the limitations of earlier techniques by providing fast detection, simple implementation, and high accuracy.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Figure 1 shows the flow chart of the proposed method. The fault signals are modelled using MATLAB software and represented in both frequency, and time domain namely the STFT. From the TFR, the significant signal parameters such as instantaneous of total waveform distortion, RMS current, total nonharmonic distortion, average current, total harmonic distortion and RMS fundamental current are estimated. The switches fault are then classified and identified using a rule-based classifier based on the signal characteristics.

2.1. Modelling of VSI switches fault

Despite the fact that overcurrent or short circuit protection against power switches has become increasingly popular on industrial drives, open circuit failures are still disregarded in the industrial context [89]. Overheating from thermic cycling, for example, can cause connections to break, which can be caused by bonding wire lifting, device driver problems, or connection breakage itself [90]. Furthermore, the OC has the ability to develop secondary faults and cause several device problems in the system if used in such an unusual manner over an extended period of time [91]. The topology of open and short circuit faults of VSI are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) depict a VSI switches fault model using MATLAB. In addition, the designed circuit has a DC voltage input of 50V, a sampling time of 100s, and a fundamental frequency of 60 Hz.

2.2. Short time Fourier transform

STFT is a significant tool for indicating a signal in both the frequency and time [84], [92]–[94]. The signal spectral characteristic in time domain can be recognized using the TFR. As a result, STFTs are an appropriate method for analyzing switch fault signals with non-stationary and multi-frequency components.

$$S_x(t, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)w(\tau - t)e^{-j2\pi f t} d\tau \quad (1)$$

where ω is the observation window.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the proposed method

Figure 2. The fault topology of VSI, (a) Open circuit switch fault at leg ‘A’, (b) short circuit switch fault at leg ‘A’

Figure 3. VSI switches fault model using MATLAB, (a) Switches fault model at leg A, (b) Fault generation module

2.3. Signal characteristic

The STFT is used to calculate signal characteristics in order to offer timely data about the signal. It is distinguished by the following parameters: total harmonic distortion mean (THD_{mean}), fault duration ($T_{d,fault}$), total non-harmonic distortion mean ($TnHD_{mean}$), average RMS current mean ($I_{rms,mean}$), average current mean ($I_{ave,mean}$), and total waveform distortion mean (TWD_{mean}). Using signal parameter information, it is then feasible to identify the faulty switch location. Furthermore, the sample frequency for the recommended approach is 10 kHz.

2.4. Ruled-based classifier

A deterministic classification, which is rule-based classifier, is widely utilized in a variety of applications due to its simplicity and ease of implementation [95]. The efficiency of the classification is strongly depending on competent threshold, and rules preferences. To classify and identify failures in the switches, a rule-based classifier based on signal characteristics is used. This study will use 60 different signals with varied characteristics of different switch fault signal in order to establish the optimum potential threshold setup parameters for the suggested technique. In addition, the total waveform distortion threshold ($TWD_{thres,fault}$) is used to calculate the threshold values of the proposed method.

$$T_{d,fault} = \int_0^T \begin{cases} 1, \text{ for } TWD(t) \geq TWD_{thres,fault} \\ 0, \text{ elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the findings of the switch faults analysis using STFT. The open switch fault take place at S_{31} of phase c upper, and the short switch fault appears at S_{12} of phase. Figures 4(a) and 4(b) depict the time and time-frequency domains of open circuit fault signals. Figure 4(a) illustrates the signal in TFR, where the red color represents the largest magnitude and the blue color represents the lowest magnitude, as seen in the contour plots. Meanwhile, Figure 4(b) depicts the magnitude of the signal as a transient reduce from 1.6A to 0.05A for a fault period of 60 ms during an open circuit fault.

Following that, a short-circuit fault of the VSI switch occurs at S_{12} and. As demonstrated in 60 Hz frequency appears along the time axis in Figure 5(a). The DC component (0 Hz) does exist, however, during the fault period, which ranges from 195ms to 255 ms. Figure 5(b) shows the signal magnitude abruptly drops from 1.6 A to 0.05 A for 60 ms between 195 ms and 255 ms.

Figure 6 depicts a graphical representation of the average current, fundamental current, and RMS current of open circuit switch faults. Starting at 195 ms and lasting 60 ms, the RMS current is reduced from 1.17 A to 0.9 A. The basic current exhibits a similar behavior, with the signal's current suddenly dropping for 60 ms. The current decline from the nominal value ranges from 1.17 to 0.7 A. Similarly, once the fault signals are recognized, the average current signal is reduced to -0.7 A. As illustrated in Figure 7(a), the RMS current for a short circuit increases abruptly to 1.35 A from the nominal value which is 1.17 A, whereas for a period of 60 ms the RMS fundamental current declines to 0.75 A. Comparable to average current, the current drops from 0 A to -1.1 A and exists at the negative cycle.

Figure 4. Switch fault at S_{31} , (a) time-frequency representation (TFR), (b) open circuit fault signals

Figure 5. Switch fault at S_{12} (a) short circuit fault signals, (b) time-frequency representation (TFR)

Figures 8(a), and 8(b) present the total waveform distortion and total nonharmonic distortion magnitude for a period 60 ms that increases from 2% to 55% and 47%, respectively. As shown in Figure 8(c), the magnitude of total harmonic distortion increases by 30% for open circuit switches fault. According to the investigation of open circuit switch faults, total nonharmonic distortion has a greater percentage value than total harmonic distortion. Total waveform distortion is the combination of total nonharmonic distortion, and total harmonic distortion.

Figure 6. Open circuit switches faults signal parameter; (a) instantaneous average current, (b) instantaneous fundamental current and (c) instantaneous rms current.

Figure 7. Short circuit switches faults signal parameter; (a) instantaneous rms current, (b) instantaneous fundamental current and (c) instantaneous average current

Figure 8. Signal parameters of open circuit switches faults; (a) instantaneous of total waveform distortion, (b) total nonharmonic distortion, and (c) total harmonic distortion

Figure 9 (a) depicts the amount of total waveform distortion or short circuit switches fault, which is identical to total nonharmonic distortion since total harmonic distortion and total nonharmonic distortion are added together. Meanwhile, as seen in Figure 9, the amount of total harmonic distortion remains low (3%). As a result of this, Figure 9 (c) depicts the total nonharmonic distortion magnitude, which increases from 4% to 55% at 180 ms for a period of 60 ms.

The fault signal was derived through the analysis of 60 signals with varied properties for each type of switch (open and short circuit for S_{11} , S_{12} , S_{21} , S_{22} , S_{31} , and S_{32}). The best threshold value for a rule-based classifier is found to be 0.05 or 5%. The pseudo code as shown in Figure 10 describes a rule-based classifier for classifying and identifying switch faults based on signal characteristics. The fault signals of switches are evaluated and classified using STFT and a rule-based method. In addition, 60 signals with various fault signal characteristics are generated to determine the system's performance. According to Table 1, the proposed technique provides 98.3% accuracy of classification.

Figure 9. Short Circuit Switches Faults Signal Parameter; (a) Instantaneous Total Waveform Distortion, (b) Total Harmonic Distortion and (c) Total Nonharmonic Distortion

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Fucntion[z]=rule_basic_classifier (Td_fault,           z = Open: S3;
Iave,mean, Irms,mean, THDave,mean, TnHDave,mean, TWDave,mean)
else if (010101)
If(011011)
z = Open: S1;
else if (100111)
z = Open: S4;
z = Open: S1;
else if (100111)
z = Open: S5;
z = Open: S2;
else if (011111)
z = Open: S6;
z = Open: S2;
else if (101101)
z = Short: S6;
z = Open: S3;
else if (0100101)
else
z = unknown
end
    
```

Figure 10. Pseudo code of a rule-based classifier for classifying and identifying switch faults

Table 1. Performance of switches faults signals classification of the proposed method

Faults	Switch	% Correct Classification
Open-Circuit	S1	98.3
	S2	98.3
	S3	98.3
	S4	98.3
	S5	98.3
	S6	98.3
Short-Circuit	S1	98.3
	S2	98.3
	S3	98.3
	S4	98.3
	S5	98.3
	S6	98.3

4. CONCLUSION

The STFT approach, in conjunction with a rule-based classifier, was used to create a classification and identification system for switch fault signals. The system's performance is then validated by categorizing 60 actual signals with varying characteristics for each sort of switch fault signal. The suggested approach performs admirably, with 98.3 percent of faults correctly classified. As a result, it shows that the system is well-suited for usage as a switch fault monitoring system. Other time-frequency domain methods, such as the Gabor transform and S-transform, should be investigated in future study to improve classification accuracy.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Vashishtha and K. R. Rekha, "Modified digital space vector pulse width modulation realization on low-cost FPGA platform with optimization for 3-phase voltage source inverter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 4. pp. 3629–3638, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i4.pp3629-3638.
- [2] P. Kiatsookkanatorn and N. Watjanatepin, "Novel ripple reduction method using three-level inverters with unipolar PWM," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 22, no. 3. pp. 1272–1283, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v22.i3.pp1272-1283.
- [3] I. Bouyakoub, R. Taleb, H. Mellah, and A. Zerglaine, "Implementation of space vector modulation for two level Three-phase inverter using dSPACE DS1104," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 20, no. 2. pp. 744–751, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i2.pp744-751.
- [4] R. G. Omar, "Modified FCS-MPC algorithm for five-leg voltage source inverter," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 19, no. 1. pp. 47–57, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v19.i1.pp47-57.
- [5] M. O. Mahmoud, W. Mamdouh, and H. Khalil, "Source current harmonic mitigation of distorted voltage source by using shunt active power filter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 4. pp. 3967–3977, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp3967-3977.
- [6] Suroso, D. T. Nugroho, A. N. Azis, and T. Noguchi, "Simplified five-level voltage source inverter with level-phase-shifted carriers based modulation technique," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 13, no. 2. pp. 461–468, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v13.i2.pp461-468.
- [7] C. Wang, A. V. Peterchev, and S. M. Goetz, "Online switch open-circuit fault diagnosis using reconfigurable scheduler for modular multilevel converter with parallel connectivity," *2019 21st European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications, EPE 2019 ECCE Europe*, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.23919/EPE.2019.8915402.
- [8] X. Liu, M. Ma, W. Guo, X. Meng, and P. Xiong, "Inverter Fault Diagnosis Based on Optimized BP Neural Network," *Proceedings of the 16th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications, ICIEA 2021*, pp. 803–808, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1109/ICIEA51954.2021.9516072.
- [9] J. A. Reyes-Malanche, F. J. Villalobos-Pina, E. Cabal-Yepez, R. Alvarez-Salas, and C. Rodriguez-Donate, "Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis in Power Inverters through Currents Analysis in Time Domain," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 70, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2021.3082325.
- [10] M. H. Jopri, A. R. Abdullah, T. Sutikno, M. Manap, and M. R. Yusoff, "A utilisation of improved gabor transform for harmonic signals detection and classification analysis," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v7i1.pp21-28.
- [11] N. M. Kassim, M. Manap, N. A. Ngatiman, M. R. Yusoff, and M. H. Jopri, "Localization of Multiple Harmonic

- Sources for Inverter Loads Utilizing Periodogram,” *J. Teknol.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 87–91.
- [12] L. R. L. V. Raj, A. Jidin, Z. Ibrahim, K. A. Karim, M. A. Said, and M. H. Jopri, “Optimal torque control performance of DTC of 5-phase induction machine.” doi: 10.1109/ICEMS.2013.6713180.
- [13] H. R. Baghaee, D. Mlakic, S. Nikolovski, and T. Dragicevic, “Anti-Islanding Protection of PV-Based Microgrids Consisting of PHEVs Using SVMs,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 483–500, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2019.2924290.
- [14] M. A. Al-Yoonus and O. S. Al-Deen Alyozbaky, “Detection of internal and external faults of single-phase induction motor using current signature,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2830–2841, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i4.pp2830-2841.
- [15] F. Babaa and O. Bennis, “An accurate inter-turn short circuit faults model dedicated to induction motors,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 9–16, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i1.pp9-16.
- [16] G. K. Kumar and D. Elangovan, “Review on fault-diagnosis and fault-tolerance for DC–DC converters,” *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1049/IET-PEL.2019.0672.
- [17] S. Bairabathina and S. Balamurugan, “Review on non-isolated multi-input step-up converters for grid-independent hybrid electric vehicles,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 41, pp. 21687–21713, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2020.05.277.
- [18] S. S. Khan and H. Wen, “A Comprehensive Review of Fault Diagnosis and Tolerant Control in DC-DC Converters for DC Microgrids,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 80100–80127, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3083721.
- [19] C. Wang, L. Zhou, and Z. Li, “Survey of switch fault diagnosis for modular multilevel converter,” *IET Circuits, Devices & Systems*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 117–124, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1049/IET-CDS.2018.5136.
- [20] A. Bakeer, A. Chub, and D. Vinnikov, “Short-Circuit Fault Detection and Remedial in Full-Bridge Rectifier of Series Resonant DC-DC Converter Based on Inductor Voltage Signature,” *2020 IEEE 61st Annual International Scientific Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University, RTUCON 2020 - Proceedings*, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/RTUCON51174.2020.9316482.
- [21] M. Ashourloo *et al.*, “Fault Detection in a Hybrid Dickson DC-DC Converter for 48-V Automotive Applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 4254–4268, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.3022764.
- [22] Y. Cheng, W. Dong, F. Gao, and G. Xin, “Open-circuit fault diagnosis of traction inverter based on compressed sensing theory,” *Chinese Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 52–60, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.23919/CJEE.2020.000004.
- [23] N. A. Ramlı, A. Jidin, Z. Rasin, and T. Sutikno, “Reduction of total harmonic distortion of three-phase inverter using alternate switching strategy,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1598–1608, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i3.pp1598-1608.
- [24] A. Chemseddine, N. Benabadji, A. Cheknane, and S. E. Mankour, “A comparison of single phase standalone square waveform solar inverter topologies: Half bridge and full bridge,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3384–3392, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp3384-3392.
- [25] H. Long, M. Ma, W. Guo, F. Li, and X. Zhang, “Fault diagnosis for IGBTs open-circuit faults in photovoltaic grid-connected inverters based on statistical analysis and machine learning,” *2020 IEEE 1st China International Youth Conference on Electrical Engineering, CIYCEE 2020*, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/CIYCEE49808.2020.9332538.
- [26] Y. Zhang, G. Liu, W. Zhao, H. Zhou, Q. Chen, and M. Wei, “Online Diagnosis of Slight Interturn Short-Circuit Fault for a Low-Speed Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor,” *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 104–113, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2020.2991271.
- [27] W. Srirattanawichaiikul, “A generalized switching function-based SVM algorithm of single-phase three-leg converter with active power decoupling,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6189–6201, 2020, doi: 10.11591/IJECE.V10I6.PP6189-6201.
- [28] K. Kamil, M. A. A. Ab Rahman, C. K. Hen, H. Hashim, and M. H. Mansor, “Analysis on the voltage stability on transmission network with pv interconnection,” *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1162–1168, 2019, doi: 10.11591/eei.v8i3.1632.
- [29] M. Kala Rathi and N. Rathina Prabha, “Grid interconnected photo voltaic system using shunt active filter for power quality improvement,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 365–376, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n1.pp365-376.
- [30] M. T. Fard, W. A. Khan, J. He, N. Weise, and M. Abarzadeh, “Fast online diagnosis of open-circuit switching faults in flying capacitor multilevel inverters,” *Chinese Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 53–62, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.23919/CJEE.2020.000030.
- [31] Z. Li, Y. Gao, H. Ma, and X. Zhang, “A Simple ANN-Based Diagnosis Method for Open-Switch Faults in Power Converters,” *IECON Proceedings (Industrial Electronics Conference)*, vol. 2020-Octob, pp. 2835–2839, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/IECON43393.2020.9254607.
- [32] Z. C. S. Yan-xia, “Open circuit fault diagnosis of dual three-phase voltage source inverter based on wavelet analysis,” *Electric Machines & Control / Dianji Yu Kongzhi Xuebao*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 65–75, 2020, doi: 10.15938/j.emc.2020.09.008.
- [33] L. R. L. V. Raj, A. Jidin, K. Abdul Karim, T. Sutikno, R. Sundram, and M. H. Jopri, “Improved torque control performance of direct torque control for 5-phase induction machine,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 391–399, 2013, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v3i4.5249.
- [34] A. F. Noor Azam *et al.*, “Current control of BLDC drives for EV application,” in *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE 7th*

- International Power Engineering and Optimization Conference, PEOCO 2013*, 2013, doi: 10.1109/PEOCO.2013.6564583.
- [35] M. Z. R. Zuber Ahmadi, A. Jidin, K. B. Jaffar, M. N. Othman, R. N. P. Nagarajan, and M. H. Jopri, "Minimization of torque ripple utilizing by 3-L CHMI in DTC." *Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE 7th International Power Engineering and Optimization Conference, PEOCO 2013*, no. June, pp. 636–640, 2013, doi: 10.1109/PEOCO.2013.6564625.
- [36] T. Shi, Y. He, T. Wang, and B. Li, "Open Switch Fault Diagnosis Method for PWM Voltage Source Rectifier Based on Deep Learning Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 66595–66608, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917311.
- [37] C. Sui, Y. He, and M. Chen, "Analysis of Current Distortion of Three-Phase Voltage Source Rectifiers and its Application in Fault Diagnosis," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 4065–4075, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2963117.
- [38] J. Liu, J. Wang, W. Yu, Z. Wang, and G. Zhong, "Open-circuit fault diagnosis of traction inverter based on improved convolutional neural network," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1633, no. 1, p. 012099, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1633/1/012099.
- [39] N. D. Thombare, "Open Switch Fault Diagnosis of Switching Devices in Three Phase VSI," *Lect. Notes Electr. Eng*, vol. 698, pp. 623–632, doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-7961-5_60.
- [40] M. A. Khelif, A. Bendiabdellah, and B. D. E. Cherif, "Short-circuit fault diagnosis of the DC-Link capacitor and its impact on an electrical drive system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2807–2814, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2807-2814.
- [41] B. O. Anyaka and I. O. Ozioko, "Transmission line short circuit analysis by impedance matrix method," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1712–1721, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp1712-1721.
- [42] K. Hu, Z. Liu, Y. Yang, F. Iannuzzo, and F. Blaabjerg, "Ensuring a Reliable Operation of Two-Level IGBT-Based Power Converters: A Review of Monitoring and Fault-Tolerant Approaches," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 89988–90022, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2994368.
- [43] S. H. Kim, D. Y. Yoo, S. W. An, Y. S. Park, J. W. Lee, and K. B. Lee, "Fault Detection Method Using a Convolution Neural Network for Hybrid Active Neutral-Point Clamped Inverters," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 140632–140642, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3011730.
- [44] M. Salehifar, R. S. Arashloo, M. Moreno-Eguilaz, V. Sala, and L. Romeral, "A simple and robust method for open switch fault detection in power converters," *Proceedings - 2013 9th IEEE International Symposium on Diagnostics for Electric Machines, Power Electronics and Drives, SDEMPED 2013*, pp. 461–468, 2013, doi: 10.1109/DEMPED.2013.6645756.
- [45] J. S. Perise, M. Bakkar, and S. B. Rodriguez, "Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis and Maintenance in Multi-Pulse Parallel and Series TRU Topologies," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 10906–10916, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.2976895.
- [46] M. Houchati, L. Ben-Brahim, A. Gastli, and N. Meskin, "Fault detection in modular multilevel converter using principle component analysis," *Proceedings - 2018 IEEE 12th International Conference on Compatibility, Power Electronics and Power Engineering, CPE-POWERENG 2018*, pp. 1–6, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1109/CPE.2018.8372596.
- [47] M. Houchati, "Fault Detection And Localization In Modular Multilevel Converter," 2018.
- [48] W. J. Kim and S. H. Kim, "Ann design of multiple open-switch fault diagnosis for three-phase pwm converters," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 19, pp. 4490–4497, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1049/IET-PEL.2020.0795.
- [49] M. Shahbazi, E. Jamshidpour, P. Poure, S. Saadate, and M. R. Zolghadri, "Open-and short-circuit switch fault diagnosis for nonisolated DC-DC converters using field programmable gate array," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 60, no. 9, pp. 4136–4146, 2013, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2012.2224078.
- [50] G. K. Kumar and D. Elangovan, "Review on fault-diagnosis and fault-tolerance for DC-DC converters," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2020, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2019.0672.
- [51] Y. Xia and Y. Xu, "A Transferrable Data-Driven Method for IGBT Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis in Three-Phase Inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 13478–13488, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3088889.
- [52] L. R. L. V. Raj, A. Jidin, C. W. M. F. C. W. M. Zalani, K. A. Karim, G. W. Yen, and M. Jopri, "Improved performance of DTC of five-phase induction machines." doi: 10.1109/PEOCO.2013.6564621.
- [53] R. Nair, A. Jidin, M. N. Othman, M. H. Jopri, and M. Manap, "Comparison performance of 3-Level and 5-Level Cascaded H-Bridge multilevel inverter of DTC of Induction Machine." doi: 10.1109/ICEMS.2013.6713181.
- [54] M. W. Ahmad, N. B. Y. Gorla, H. Malik, and S. K. Panda, "A Fault Diagnosis and Postfault Reconfiguration Scheme for Interleaved Boost Converter in PV-Based System," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 3769–3780, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.3018540.
- [55] S. Zhuo, A. Gaillard, L. Xu, C. Liu, D. Paire, and F. Gao, "An Observer-Based Switch Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis of DC-DC Converter for Fuel Cell Application," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 3159–3167, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2020.2978752.
- [56] S. Tang *et al.*, "Detection and Identification of Power Switch Failures Using Discrete Fourier Transform for DC-DC Flying Capacitor Buck Converters," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4062–4071, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2020.3012201.
- [57] M. R. Ab. Ghani, M. H. Jopri, and M. R. Yusoff, "A critical review of time-frequency distribution analysis for detection and classification of harmonic signal in power distribution system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 4603–4618, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i6.pp.4603-4618.

- [58] P. Kumar, G. S. Brar, S. Singh, S. Nikolovski, H. R. Baghaee, and Z. Balkić, “Perspectives and Intensification of Energy Efficiency in Commercial and Residential Buildings Using Strategic Auditing and Demand-Side Management,” *Energies* 2019, Vol. 12, Page 4539, vol. 12, no. 23, p. 4539, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.3390/EN12234539.
- [59] P. Li, X. Li, and T. Zeng, “A Fast and Simple Fault Diagnosis Method for Interleaved DC-DC Converters Based on Output Voltage Analysis,” *Electronics* 2021, Vol. 10, Page 1451, vol. 10, no. 12, p. 1451, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ELECTRONICS10121451.
- [60] T. Berghout, M. Benbouzid, T. Bentrçia, X. Ma, S. Djurović, and L.-H. Mouss, “Machine Learning-Based Condition Monitoring for PV Systems: State of the Art and Future Prospects,” *Energies* 2021, Vol. 14, Page 6316, vol. 14, no. 19, p. 6316, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/EN14196316.
- [61] S. Cheng *et al.*, “An open-circuit fault-diagnosis method for inverters based on phase current,” *Transportation Safety and Environment*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 148–160, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1093/TSE/TDAA008.
- [62] N. . Abidullah, “Analysis of Power Quality Disturbances Using Spectrogram and S-transform,” *International Review of Electrical Engineering (IREE)*, vol. 3, no. June, pp. 611–619, 2014.
- [63] S. Sahoo, J. K. Das, and B. Debnath, “Rolling element bearing condition monitoring using filtered acoustic emission,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 5. pp. 3560–3567, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i5.pp3560-3567.
- [64] M. H. Jopri, A. R. Abdullah, M. Manap, T. Sutikno, and M. R. A. Ghani, “Harmonic contribution analysis of electric arc furnace by using spectrogram,” *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 7, no. 2. pp. 236–243, 2018, doi: 10.11591/eei.v7i2.1187.
- [65] A. Achmamad and A. Jbari, “A comparative study of wavelet families for electromyography signal classification based on discrete wavelet transform,” *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 4. pp. 1420–1429, 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i4.2381.
- [66] I. Aizenberg *et al.*, “A Neural Network Classifier with Multi-Valued Neurons for Analog Circuit Fault Diagnosis,” *Electronics* 2021, Vol. 10, Page 349, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 349, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ELECTRONICS10030349.
- [67] A. M. Silveira and R. E. Araújo, “A new approach for the diagnosis of different types of faults in dc-dc power converters based on inversion method,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 180, p. 106103, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.EPSR.2019.106103.
- [68] A. E. Labrador Rivas and T. Abrão, “Faults in smart grid systems: Monitoring, detection and classification,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 189, p. 106602, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.EPSR.2020.106602.
- [69] H. Abouobaida and Y. Abouelmahjoub, “New Diagnosis and Fault-Tolerant Control Strategy for Photovoltaic System,” *International Journal of Photoenergy*, vol. 2021, 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/8075165.
- [70] J. Yang and C. Delpha, “Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis for Interleaved DC-DC Converters,” *IECON Proceedings (Industrial Electronics Conference)*, vol. 2020-October, pp. 3982–3987, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/IECON43393.2020.9255288.
- [71] M. H. Jopri, A. R. Abdullah, M. Manap, M. R. Yusoff, T. Sutikno, and M. F. Habban, “An improved detection and classification technique of harmonic signals in power distribution by utilizing spectrogram,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v7i1.pp12-20.
- [72] D. Mlakić, S. Nikolovski, and Z. Baus, “Detection of faults in electrical panels using deep learning method,” in *2017 International Conference on Smart Systems and Technologies (SST)*, 2017, pp. 55–61.
- [73] W. J. Mattos and R. E. Araujo, “Fault diagnosis in DC-DC power converters based on parity equations,” *Proceedings - 2020 International Young Engineers Forum, YEF-ECE 2020*, pp. 13–18, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1109/YEF-ECE49388.2020.9171806.
- [74] Y. Yu, Y. Jiang, Y. Liu, and X. Peng, “Incipient fault diagnosis method for dc-dc converters based on sensitive fault features,” *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 19, pp. 4646–4658, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1049/IET-PEL.2020.0857.
- [75] S. Jagtap and D. More, “Switch Open-circuit Fault Diagnosis and Fault-Tolerant Control Strategy for DC-DC Converters,” *Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing, ICCSP 2020*, pp. 1399–1405, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICCSP48568.2020.9182063.
- [76] L. Xu, R. Ma, R. Xie, J. Xu, Y. Huangfu, and F. Gao, “Open-Circuit Switch Fault Diagnosis and Fault-Tolerant Control for Output-Series Interleaved Boost DC-DC Converter,” *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 2054–2066, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2021.3083811.
- [77] T. Wang, C. Wang, X. Zhou, and H. Chen, “An overview of FPGA based deep learning accelerators: Challenges and opportunities,” *Proceedings - 21st IEEE International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications, 17th IEEE International Conference on Smart City and 5th IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Systems, HPCC/SmartCity/DSS 2019*, pp. 1674–1681, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1109/HPCC/SMARTCITY/DSS.2019.00229.
- [78] J. Hoozemans, J. Peltenburg, F. Nonnemacher, A. Hadnagy, Z. Al-Ars, and H. P. Hofstee, “FPGA Acceleration for Big Data Analytics: Challenges and Opportunities,” *IEEE Circuits and Systems Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 30–47, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1109/MCAS.2021.3071608.
- [79] G. Furano *et al.*, “Towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence on the Edge in Space Systems: Challenges and Opportunities,” *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 44–56, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1109/MAES.2020.3008468.
- [80] R. Palanisamy, C. S. Boopathi, K. Selvakumar, and K. Vijayakumar, “Switching pulse generation for DC-DC boost converter using Xilinx-ISE with FPGA processor,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 2. pp. 1722–1727, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp1722-1727.

- [81] A. R. Ajel, H. M. A. Abbas, and M. J. Mnati, "Position and speed optimization of servo motor control through FPGA," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1. pp. 319–327, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i1.pp319-327.
- [82] H. M. A. Abbas, R. F. Chisab, and M. J. Mnati, "Monitoring and controlling the speed and direction of a DC motor through FPGA and comparison of FPGA for speed and performance optimization," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 5. pp. 3903–3912, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i5.pp3903-3912.
- [83] S. A. A. Tarusan, A. Jidin, M. L. M. Jamil, K. A. Karim, and T. Sutikno, "A review of direct torque control development in various multilevel inverter applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 11, no. 3. pp. 1675–1688, 2020, doi: 10.11591/IJPEDS.V11.I3.PP1675-1688.
- [84] F. A. F. Hlawatsch, *Time-Frequency Analysis: Concepts and Methods*, 1st Editio. Wiley-ISTE, 2008.
- [85] T. Jiang, Y. Wang, and Z. Li, "Fault Diagnosis of Three-Phase Inverter Based on CEEMDAN and GWO-SVM," *Proceedings - 2020 Chinese Automation Congress, CAC 2020*, pp. 2362–2368, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/CAC51589.2020.9327856.
- [86] S. Lei *et al.*, "A Diagnostic Technique for Open-switch Fault of Inverters Based on Three-channel 2D-CNN," *Ship & Ocean Engineering*, no. 1, pp. 78–82, 2020.
- [87] M. F. B. Habbab, M. Manap, A. R. Abdullah, M. H. Jopri, and T. Sutikno, "An evaluation of linear time frequency distribution analysis for VSI switch faults identification," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijped.v8i1.pp1-9.
- [88] A. R. R. Abdullah, N. S. S. Ahmad, N. Bahari, M. Manap, A. Jidin, and M. H. Jopri, "Short-circuit switches fault analysis of voltage source inverter using spectrogram," in *Electr. Mach. Syst. (ICEMS), 2013 Int. Conf*, pp. 1808–1813.
- [89] U. Choi, J. Lee, F. Blaabjerg, and K. Lee, "Open-Circuit Fault Diagnosis and Fault-Tolerant Control for a Grid-Connected NPC Inverter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 31, no. 10, pp. 7234–7247, 2016, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2015.2510224.
- [90] B. Mirafzal, "Survey of Fault-Tolerance Techniques for Three-Phase Voltage Source Inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 10, pp. 5192–5202, 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2014.2301712.
- [91] J. O. Estima and A. J. M. Cardoso, "A new approach for real-time multiple open-circuit fault diagnosis in voltage source inverters," in *2010 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition*, 2010, pp. 4328–4335, doi: 10.1109/ECCE.2010.5618462.
- [92] J. S. Ashwin and N. Manoharan, "Audio denoising based on short time fourier transform," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 9, no. 1. pp. 89–92, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v9.i1.pp89-92.
- [93] S. Myint and W. Wichakool, "A high frequency reflected current signals-based fault type identification method," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 17, no. 2. pp. 551–563, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v17.i2.pp551-563.
- [94] T. Y. Jun, A. B. Jambek, and U. Hashim, "Performance analysis of low-complexity welch power spectral density for automatic frequency analyser," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 8, no. 1. pp. 99–104, 2019, doi: 10.11591/eei.v8i1.1393.
- [95] H. Ishibuchi, Y. Hitotsuyanagi, Noritaka Tsukamoto, and Yusuke Nojima, "Use of Heuristic Local Search for Single-Objective Optimization in Multiobjective Memetic Algorithms," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 2008, pp. 743–752, doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-87700-4_74.

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